

e-ISSN: 3107-944X

Volume 02 Issue 02
May-Aug, 2026

***Corresponding**

**Author: Kompally
Nikshitha,**
Students, Department of
Computer Science &
Engineering, Mahatma
Gandhi Institute of
Technology, Hyderabad,
Telangana, India

AI-Based Traffic Violation Detection and Ambulance Path Clearance System

**Kompally Nikshitha*¹, Mohammed Sony², DR. Sri Kala³,
N. Rama Krishna⁴**

¹⁻³ Students, ⁴ Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science
& Engineering, Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Technology,
Hyderabad, Telangana, India

Abstract

Traffic violations, traffic congestion, and delayed emergency response are major challenges in modern urban transportation systems. Traditional traffic monitoring and control methods rely heavily on manual observation, resulting in slow response times and inefficient traffic management. This project presents an AI-Based Traffic Violation Detection and Ambulance Path Clearance System to enhance road safety and improve emergency vehicle movement.

The proposed system uses live video feeds from CCTV or IP cameras and applies computer vision techniques using deep learning models such as YOLOv8 to detect vehicles, traffic signals, and emergency vehicles. Traffic violations including signal jumping, helmetless riding, wrong-lane driving, triple riding, and overspeeding are automatically identified. For each detected violation, the system generates digital evidence in the form of photos along with timestamps and vehicle details, enabling reliable verification and enforcement.

The system also performs ambulance detection, where emergency vehicles are identified in real time and traffic signals are automatically controlled to clear the path, ensuring faster and uninterrupted movement. In addition, traffic signal timing is dynamically adjusted based on traffic flow density to reduce congestion.

A centralized dashboard at the traffic control office allows authorities to monitor violations, view evidence, track traffic conditions, and oversee ambulance movement in real time. This project demonstrates the effective use of artificial intelligence for intelligent traffic management, improved emergency response, and safer urban road environments.

Keywords:- CCTV or IP cameras and applies computer vision techniques using deep learning models such as YOLOv8 to detect vehicles

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, rapid urbanization and population growth have significantly increased the number of vehicles on roads, leading to complex challenges in traffic management. Traffic congestion, frequent rule violations, and delayed emergency response have become major concerns in metropolitan and developing cities alike. These issues not only waste time and fuel but also contribute to environmental

pollution and increase the risk of road accidents. Efficient traffic management has therefore become essential to ensure smooth transportation, public safety, and timely emergency services.

Traditional traffic monitoring and control systems rely heavily on manual observation by traffic personnel and fixed-timing traffic signals. While these systems have been in use for decades, they suffer from several limitations such as human error, limited scalability, and delayed response to real-time situations. Manual monitoring is not only labor-intensive but also inefficient in handling large volumes of traffic data. Moreover, conventional systems lack the ability to adapt dynamically to changing traffic conditions, resulting in increased congestion and ineffective enforcement of traffic regulations.

With the advancement of artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), and computer vision technologies, intelligent traffic management systems have emerged as a promising solution to these challenges. These technologies enable automated analysis of realtime data captured from surveillance cameras, allowing for accurate detection, classification, and tracking of vehicles. Deep learning models, particularly object detection algorithms such as YOLO (You Only Look Once), have demonstrated high efficiency and accuracy in recognizing objects within video streams, making them ideal for traffic monitoring

applications.

The proposed **AI-Based Traffic Violation Detection and Ambulance Path Clearance System** leverage these advancements to create a smart and automated traffic management solution. The system utilizes live video feeds from CCTV or IP cameras installed at road intersections and highways. These video streams are processed using deep learning models like YOLOv8 to detect various elements such as vehicles, traffic signals, road lanes, and emergency vehicles in real time.

One of the primary objectives of this system is to automatically detect traffic violations. Common violations such as signal jumping, helmetless riding, wrong-lane driving, triple riding on two-wheelers, and overspeeding are identified using computer vision techniques. Unlike manual enforcement, this automated approach ensures continuous monitoring without fatigue and minimizes the chances of human error. For each detected violation, the system captures digital evidence in the form of images or video clips along with timestamps and vehicle details. This evidence can be used by authorities for verification, issuing penalties, and maintaining records, thereby improving transparency and accountability in traffic law enforcement.

Another significant feature of the system is its ability to prioritize emergency vehicles, particularly ambulances. Delays in

ambulance movement due to traffic congestion can have life-threatening consequences. The proposed system addresses this issue by detecting ambulances in real time using visual recognition techniques. Once an ambulance is identified, the system automatically adjusts traffic signals along its route to provide a clear and uninterrupted path. This intelligent signal control mechanism ensures faster response times and can play a crucial role in saving

lives during medical emergencies. In addition to violation detection and emergency vehicle prioritization, the system also incorporates adaptive traffic signal control based on traffic density. By analyzing the number of vehicles at different lanes or intersections, the system dynamically adjusts signal timings to optimize traffic flow. For example, lanes with higher vehicle density are given longer green signals, while less congested lanes receive shorter durations. This real-time adjustment helps reduce traffic congestion, waiting times, and fuel consumption, contributing to a more efficient and eco-friendly transportation system. To provide effective control and monitoring, the system includes a centralized dashboard accessible to traffic authorities. This dashboard displays real-time traffic data, detected violations, captured evidence, and the status of emergency vehicle movement. Authorities can use this interface to monitor multiple locations simultaneously, review incidents, and make informed decisions. The integration of such a centralized system enhances coordination, improves response time, and simplifies traffic management operations. Furthermore, the implementation of this system supports the concept of smart cities, where technology is used to improve the quality of urban life. By automating traffic monitoring and management, the system reduces the workload on traffic personnel and enables them to focus on more critical tasks. It also promotes safer driving behavior among citizens by ensuring strict and consistent enforcement of traffic rules. In conclusion, the **AI- Based Traffic Violation Detection and Ambulance Path Clearance System** represent a significant step toward modernizing urban traffic management. By combining artificial intelligence, computer vision, and real-

time data processing, the system addresses key challenges such as traffic violations, congestion, and delayed emergency response. The adoption of such intelligent systems can lead to safer roads, improved traffic efficiency, and enhanced emergency services, ultimately contributing to the development of smarter and more sustainable cities.

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3. DESIGN METHODOLOGY:

The flow diagram represents the working process of the AI-Based Traffic Violation Detection and Ambulance Path Clearance System, showing how data is captured, processed, and utilized for intelligent traffic management.

The system begins with input data collection, where live video feeds are obtained from CCTV or IP cameras installed at traffic intersections. These video streams contain real-time information about vehicles, road conditions, and traffic signals. Next, the system performs object detection and analysis using deep learning models such as YOLOv8 along with OpenCV.

The model detects vehicles, traffic signals, and road lanes from the video frames. Based on this detection, the system identifies various traffic violations including signal jumping, speeding, triple riding, and wrong-lane driving. Multiple vehicles are tracked simultaneously, and bounding boxes are drawn around detected objects for accurate monitoring.

It captures images of the violating vehicle along with important details such as timestamp and vehicle information. This ensures that each violation is recorded with proper proof for proceeds to **evidence generation**.

The collected data is then stored in a **central database**, which maintains records of all violations and corresponding evidence. The database helps in easy retrieval, analysis, and enforcement by authorities.

To enhance usability, a **dashboard**

monitoring system is integrated. This dashboard provides a signal operations based on AI decisions. visual interface for traffic authorities to monitor real- time traffic conditions, view detected violations, and access stored evidence. It helps in making quick and informed decisions.

The system also incorporates **Optical Character Recognition (OCR)** using tools like EasyOCR to extract vehicle number plates from images. This all identification of vehicles involved in violations.

4. SYSTEM FLOW:

Start: The system initiates the traffic monitoring and management process.

For hardware integration, an **Arduino UNO** is used to control traffic signals. The system communicates with the Arduino to manage

A key feature of the system is **ambulance detection and path clearance**. When an ambulance is detected in the video feed, the system prioritizes it by controlling traffic signals to provide a clear path. This ensures faster and uninterrupted

movement of emergency vehicles, reducing response time.

Capture Traffic Video: Live video is captured from CCTV cameras or demo video sources installed at traffic intersections.

AI-Based Video Analysis: The captured video is processed using AI models (such as YOLOv8) to analyze traffic scenes.

Detect Vehicles & Signals: Vehicles, traffic signals, and road conditions are identified from the video frames.

Check Traffic Rules: The system evaluates whether any traffic violations, such as signal jumping or overspeeding, have occurred.

Violation Detected: If a violation is detected, the system proceeds to generate evidence. Otherwise, it continues monitoring traffic.

Generate Evidence: Images of the violation are captured along with timestamps and vehicle details to create digital evidence.

Store Evidence in Database: All violation records and evidence data are saved in a centralized database for enforcement and review.

Display on Authority Dashboard: Traffic control authorities can monitor violations and overall traffic conditions

via a centralized dashboard.

Chatbot Query Support: A chatbot interface allows authorities to query violation details based on vehicle color, type, or other attributes.

Check for Ambulance: The system scans the video feed to detect the presence of an ambulance or emergency vehicle.

Ambulance Detected: If an ambulance is detected, the system initiates path clearance procedures; otherwise, normal traffic continues.

Send Command to Arduino: Commands are sent to an Arduino UNO device to control traffic signals for ambulance path clearance. **Arduino Controls**

Traffic Signals: The Arduino adjusts traffic signal LEDs to clear

the path, ensuring faster movement of emergency vehicles.

End: The process completes the current cycle and loops continuously for traffic monitoring and management.

5. IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation of the proposed system involves several key components: video acquisition, AI-based detection, evidence generation, database management, traffic signal control, and

ambulance path clearance.

1. Video Acquisition: Live traffic video is captured using CCTV or IP cameras installed at intersections. For demo purposes, prerecorded traffic videos can also be used. The video frames serve

as the input for the AI system.

2. AI-Based Detection: The system uses deep learning models, specifically YOLOv8, to detect vehicles, traffic signals, and road lanes. Computer vision libraries such as OpenCV process the video frames, identify objects, and track vehicle movement in real time. Various traffic violations such as signal jumping, overspeeding, wrong-lane driving, helmetless riding, and triple riding are detected automatically.

3. Evidence Generation: When a violation is detected, the system captures the vehicle image, timestamp, and relevant details. Optical Character Recognition (OCR) using EasyOCR extracts vehicle number plates from images. All this data is stored digitally as evidence for enforcement purposes.

4. Database Management and Dashboard: All violation records and evidence are stored in a centralized database. A monitoring dashboard displays real-time traffic conditions, violations, and

5.1 Tools and Technologies Used:

- **Python** for AI and video processing
- **YOLOv8** for object detection
- **OpenCV** for image and video frame processing
- **EasyOCR** for vehicle number plate recognition
- **Database (MySQL/SQLite)** for storing violation records
- **Dashboard** for real-time monitoring

5.2 Hardware Requirement:

Arduino UNO for traffic signal control ambulance status. Authorities can query violations based on vehicle type, color, or number plate using the integrated chatbot.

5. Traffic Signal Control: An Arduino UNO is interfaced with the system to control traffic signals. Based on

AI analysis, the system can adjust signal timing dynamically to reduce congestion or clear the path for emergency vehicles.

6. Ambulance Detection and Path Clearance: The system continuously scans for ambulances in the video feed. When detected, the AI model triggers traffic signal adjustments via Arduino to provide a clear path, ensuring faster movement of emergency vehicles.

7. Real-Time Operation: The entire system works in real time, processing video frames continuously, detecting violations, updating the dashboard, and controlling traffic signals. This integration ensures efficient traffic management, reduces congestion, improves road safety, and prioritizes emergency response.

5.3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Accuracy:0.8

CONCLUSION:

The AI-Based Traffic Violation Detection and Ambulance Path Clearance System provide an effective and intelligent solution to the challenges of modern urban transportation. By leveraging advanced computer vision techniques and deep learning models like YOLOv8, the system automates the detection of traffic violations with high accuracy and

reliability, reducing the dependency on manual monitoring and minimizing human error.

The integration of real-time ambulance detection and automated traffic signal control ensures faster emergency response by providing a clear and uninterrupted path for emergency vehicles. Additionally,

the dynamic adjustment of traffic signal timings based on vehicle density helps in reducing traffic congestion and improving overall traffic flow efficiency.

The centralized dashboard further enhances system usability by enabling authorities to monitor, analyze, and respond to traffic conditions and violations in real time. Overall, this project demonstrates how artificial intelligence can significantly improve road safety, optimize traffic management, and support life-saving emergency services, making urban transportation systems smarter and more efficient.

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